

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

INTERNAL REPORTING ON THE SOCIAL EXPENSES OF THE ENTERPRISE

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Abstract

This article provides important recommendations on forming internal reporting related to the social expenses of enterprises. In addition, it discusses corporate social responsibility, described as socially-oriented relationships intended to reflect the level of enterprises' obligations in the field of social protection.

Keywords: Social expenses, social responsibility, corporate social reporting, social charter, corporate social responsibility, labor standards, sustainability reporting.

Introduction. Despite a decade of long-term support, our country has managed to achieve significant accomplishments. When the ideas of corporate social reporting began to spread in our country, enterprises already had a comprehensive set of various unified approaches outlined in the country's strategic international documents. These include reporting systems already applied in foreign practice, initial corrections, and the key documents on social and environmental assessments that have passed the trial stage. For instance, in the arsenal of the Russian business community, there exists a document that is universally applicable due to its characteristics: the "Social Charter of Russian Business." This document was developed in accordance with international regulations. Based on the analysis, it can be concluded that the Social Charter of Russian Business can serve as a universal platform for reporting.

Literature review. Corporate social responsibility (CSR), described as socially-oriented relationships intended to reflect the level of enterprises' obligations in the field of social protection, emerged in the 1970s and 1980s. In the 20th century, it gained prominence in Western countries, particularly those occupying leading positions in the global economy, and stood out as a distinct direction. The reasons for its emergence can be attributed to the following factors: an increase in public negative sentiment towards business (environmental degradation, child labor exploitation, corruption, etc.), the importance of enhancing a company's reputation, a decrease in state spending for social needs (for example, Reagan's policy of new federalism), and the emergence of a moral market value as a business element.

In 1995, a non-governmental and non-profit organization, the City Economy Institute Fund, was established in Moscow. The institute serves as an economic analysis center, with its primary tasks being the analysis of socio-economic issues in the development of municipalities, the development of practical proposals and recommendations for the reform of regional and urban economies, and assisting in the implementation of specific projects.

In recent decades, the processes of globalization have led companies to take a more active role in social activities. However, the problem remains urgent. Evidence of violations by employers of international human rights and labor standards, gross violations of the

social and labor rights of employees as stipulated in legal documents, low wages, long-term wage arrears, excessive cost-cutting in health and safety investments, and worker health protection are indicators of this issue. Furthermore, this issue does not avoid key areas such as accounting, social responsibility, and its reflection in reports. For example, questions such as whether a business can be socially responsible and how social responsibility is reflected in reporting are being discussed.

Corporate social responsibility refers to the obligation of business entities to adhere to standards and norms not directly stipulated by laws or entirely unspecified (in areas such as ethics, ecology, humanitarianism, compassion, etc.), and their responsibility and impact on society and its individual social groups' quality of life. An interesting example of an initiative in the field of social responsibility is the "Darya" enterprise, established in St. Petersburg in 2002, which provided one-time aid of 1,000 rubles for advertising purposes to all girls named Darya[1].

Research Methodology. Our research was conducted with the goal of improving social responsibility activities. Tasks related to organizing and enhancing social responsibility activities were defined. During the research process, methods such as comparing practical materials and utilizing statistics were employed to develop conclusions and recommendations.

Analysis and Results. The decision to engage in responsible social business is linked to the necessity of changes in business activities, which are connected to the genuine development of society and the ongoing processes of globalization in market relations. Currently, companies that have chosen responsible business practices and sustainable development as their goal must meet the needs of shareholders and stakeholders not only on Earth but also in space[1].

Thus, non-financial reporting (social reporting, sustainability reporting) is a documented collection of information that reflects a company's scope of existence, the principles and methods of cooperation with its impact groups, and the results of activities in the economic, environmental, and social sectors, including the environmental aspects of society.

As defined by the Global Reporting Initiative – an independent international organization – "Sustainability reporting" refers to a report that covers a company's economic, environmental, and social dimensions[2].

The principles of the Global Reporting Initiative report can be divided into four main groups (Figure 1)[3].

Figure 1 – Reporting Principles According to GRI 3 Standard [4]

Thus, after reviewing the GRI reporting principles in detail, the following can be emphasized:

- ✚ the main principles for preparing social reports are transparency, stakeholder engagement, and auditability;
- ✚ principles that determine what should be included in a social report involve the context of sustainable development (economy + environment + social sphere), as well as completeness;
- ✚ principles for ensuring the quality and reliability of social reports include balance, objectivity, comparability, and accuracy;
- ✚ principles related to the availability of the social report characterize its timeliness and clarity.

It is worth noting that social reporting standards provide for the use of IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards), in particular, the sustainability reporting guidelines developed by GRI, which contain requirements for preparing economic indicators and reporting socially based on relevant IFRS standards and their interpretations.

According to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS), social reports prepared by corporations should include the following:

- ✓ Corporate objectives related to social policy;
- ✓ A system for coordinating and managing the effectiveness of its activities;
- ✓ General indicators of corporations' performance in areas such as workplace safety, labor and labor relations, environmental protection and restoration, as well as the content of social programs for cooperation with external contractors, organization of labor, and employee health protection.

The procedure for preparing financial reports consists of several stages (see Figure 2).

The preparation and publication of corporate social reports show that these are not merely quick summaries of charitable activities or socially-oriented work. At the same time, alongside the preparation of the report, corporations are also engaged in modifying their social activities in accordance with the expectations and interests of their business partners and other stakeholders.

Figure 2 – Stages of Preparing Financial Reports

It should be emphasized that social reporting itself involves the improvement of financial and managerial

accounting, as well as IFRS. For example, the first social report in Russia was prepared in 2002 by British

American Tobacco, and in 2003, such reports were prepared by Alfa-Bank, Fia-Bank, Yukos, and Sibneft

Today, there are many examples of social reporting. For instance, OJSC TKK Norilsk Nickel has been publishing social reports since 2005 to inform the public about the company's activities in the areas related to sustainable development, including its principles, objectives, practical results, and future prospects. The annual practice of preparing social and CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) reports allows for the development of a corporate social reporting system in line with international standards, provides a new perspective on corporate governance efficiency, and enhances the company's policy on corporate social responsibility.

Information about a company's activities in environmental protection, ecological safety, resource conservation, and socio-economic development of the region has sparked great public interest.

Public interest is also piqued by information on taxes paid by corporations to various levels of government budgets; their participation in regional social programs; support for war and labor veterans; involvement in youth education; support for sports and physical education; and charitable activities. The introduction of modern management systems that ensure the formation of social reports in local business activities leads to the scientific substantiation of the concept of accounting and reporting in the corporate social responsibility and non-financial reporting systems.

It is not possible to prepare a social report without maintaining a social account: social reporting data is based on accounting data. On the other hand, the requirements set by social reporters have already predetermined the accounting paradigm: currently, accounting data alone is not sufficient for forming social reports, and accounting cannot be the most important provider of the information needed to prepare social reports.

It should be emphasized that in Russia, the social indicators of entrepreneurial activity must be seriously considered when making management decisions. In our opinion, the main motivation for Russian companies in preparing social reports today is their desire to become international corporations. Thus, the number of companies involved in social reporting can primarily increase due to large holdings planning to enter international markets. At the same time, conducting socially responsible business helps prevent social problems from becoming crises that could negatively impact a company's operations. For this, it is necessary to develop a comprehensive system for accounting social and environmental indicators.

Therefore, considering the Russian model of corporate social responsibility (CSR), it can be noted that, at present, it is focused on the state, employees, and owners, but when society matures, local communities, consumers, and other stakeholders will be involved. The approach to CSR in Russia needs to be broader and more pragmatic.

Social reporting is necessary for the following purposes:

- Informing the public about the economic, environmental, and social results of the company's activities;

- Conducting independent evaluations in the above-mentioned areas;

- Engaging with all stakeholder groups, identifying their interests, assessments, and expectations;

- Preventing potential accusations;

- Gaining competitive advantages;

- Building trust among employees, shareholders, partners, customers, local communities, government authorities, and the media.

Adherence to the principles of fairness and social responsibility expressed in the specific initiatives in social reports based on international social standards indicates the potential for business development. Thus, companies can do the best work they can, creating innovations that help preserve our planet.

Often, companies have well-developed branch networks, which makes maintaining social records more challenging. Moreover, the branches are usually located in different regions, which could distort the idea of social costs. In such cases, one region may be more in need of certain social programs, while another may require different ones. To implement effective management accounting, it is necessary to develop a universal approach to preparing internal social reports.

Conclusion and Recommendations. As a result of the research, it can be concluded that specialists in accounting from various countries are paying increasing attention to social issues. This trend is a natural reaction to several global developments: the intensification of economic globalization, the expansion of the influence of transnational corporations, the growing need to legally protect members of societies in which production facilities are located, and the public's growing distrust in financial reporting figures.

This is further confirmed by the fact that, among publications on corporate social responsibility, 16 authors (or 7.62%) emphasized the importance of improving the reliability of financial reporting.

If individuals responsible for organizing and maintaining accounting possess high ethical standards, then accounting can become an integral part of corporate social responsibility (CSR). This mindset should be instilled in them from the very first days of learning their profession.

Representatives of the sociological direction in accounting even consider it necessary to expand the scope of accounting. According to them, "not only the individual enterprise but a specific society should be considered, and the accountant should not only calculate the company's profits but also assess the socio-economic consequences of the company management's actions." For example, calculating factory costs alone is not sufficient—the ecological consequences of producing that product should also be taken into account.

While we do not fully agree with this approach, we do believe that enterprises must take responsibility for expenses aimed at reducing the negative impact of their activities on society and the natural environment—and these should be reflected in the accounting system as separate cost items.

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